

NATURAL TEXTILE FIBRES: VEGETABLE FIBRES.

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Introduction

Natural fibres have been used to make textiles since prehistoric times and are still used today. Nowadays, natural fibres including animal (protein) fibres and vegetable (cellulose) fibres make up almost 50% of the textile fibres produced annually in the world. Vegetable fibre is extracted from plants. Cellulose is the main content of vegetable fibre; therefore, vegetable fibre is usually referred to as plant fibre or natural cellulosic fibre. The categories of natural cellulose fibre include:

- seed fibres (such as cotton, kapok, milkweed, etc.)

- bast fibres (such as flax, ramie, jute, kenaf, hemp, etc.)

- leaf fibres (such as sisal, pineapple, abaca, etc.) and -nut husk fibre (such as coir). In addition to cotton, the most commonly used natural vegetable fibres include flax, ramie, jute, kenaf, and sisal. Nowadays, more and more new natural fibres, especially vegetable fibre sources, are being exploited, for example, kapok, pineapple, and apocynum.

Cellulose is a linear polymer, or long chain molecule, combining several 1000 anhydroglucose units. Although glucose, a simple sugar, is soluble in water, cellulose is not due to its huge polymolecule size. Cellulose is a carbohydrate, composed of carbon (44.4%), hydrogen (6.2%), and oxygen (49.4%); the cellulose molecule with the basic units of cellobiose is shown in [Figure 1](#)

Figure 1 Diagram of cellulose molecule.

Cellobiose is formed by two combined glucose units; many cellobiose units combine to form cellulose. The number of anhydroglucose units in the cellulose molecule is referred to as the degree of polymerization. Each repeating unit equals $2n$, or two anhydroglucose units. These units are flipped over as they combine together, as shown in Figure 1

Cellulose molecules form into fibrils, or bundles of molecular chains that combine in groups to form the cellulose fibres. Each fibre is composed of many cellulose molecules. These are not arranged in a completely parallel manner; or rather although certain portions of the fibre may have the molecules lying parallel other areas are characterized by a somewhat random molecular arrangement. The parts of the fibre where molecules lie side by side and are held together by many associated forces are called crystalline. If the molecules, as well as lying side by side, are parallel to the longitudinal axis, there is a high degree of molecular orientation. Usually, high orientation and crystallinity imply strength, rigidity, low elongation, and low pliability. The strength of cellulose fibres is also influenced by the degree of polymerization (dp) as well as by the molecular arrangement. The higher the dp, the stronger the fibre. A typical degree of polymerization for a native cellulose fibre is about 10,000; for regenerated cellulose, such as rayon, it is only about 500. The molecules within the fibre are usually held in place by hydrogen bonding. When cellulose fibres are bent, the hydrogen bonds are broken, and new ones form, causing creases or wrinkles that do not hang out. This is why all products made from cellulose fibres have the same tendency to crease. Removal of the hydroxyl unit may result in cross-linking of the cellulose molecules so that they are more stable, helping to form cellulose fibres that

have a higher resistance to and recovery from creasing. Because of the hydroxyl (–OH) groups in cellulose, these fibres usually have a high attraction for water. This means that in hot weather, perspiration from the body will be absorbed in fabrics made from cellulose fibres, transported along the yarns to the outer surface of the cloth, and evaporated into the air. Thus, the body maintains its temperature and feels comfortable. Cellulose fibres also tend to burn easily and fast with a yellow flame, giving off a smell like burning paper or leaves, then depositing a light, fluffy, greyish residue or ash. Cellulose is usually decomposed by acid solutions, especially strong mineral acids, but it has excellent resistance to alkaline solutions. In general, cellulose is low in elasticity and resilience, so it is prone to creasing unless treated. The fibres are laundered readily and can withstand strong detergents, high temperatures, and bleaches (if used properly). This group of fibres is seldom damaged by insects, but fungi, such as mildew, will destroy cellulose or at least stain it severely.

DEFINITIONS AND TYPES OF COTTON

Cotton is the most popular natural fibre, accounting for around 90% of all natural fibres. Cotton is one of the most important natural textile fibre crops, both from the agricultural and manufacturing sectors' points of view. It is the biggest source of clothing as well as being used to produce apparel, home furnishings, and industrial products. The main countries producing cotton in the world are China, United States, India, Pakistan, Uzbekistan, Turkey, and Brazil, which together account for over 80 % of the world's cotton production. There are many varieties of cotton, and each variety has different characteristics both in planting and processing performance. Cotton fibres may be classified roughly into three large groups based on staple length (average length of the fibres making up a sample or bale of cotton) and appearance. **1.** Long-staple cotton is a fine, lustrous fibre with typical staple length ranging from about 30 to 40mm, and includes types of the highest quality, such as Sea Island, Egyptian, and Pima cottons. Due to the difficulty in its cultivation and its limited production, long-staple cottons are costly and are used mainly for fine fabrics, yarns, and hosiery. **2.** Medium-staple cotton is plentiful and standard, such as American Upland, with

staple length from about 25 to 33 mm. Medium-staple cotton provides about 90% of the current world production of raw cotton fibre. This fibre is widely used for apparel, home furnishings, and industrial products. **3.** Short-staple is coarse cotton, ranging from about 10 to 25mm in length, which makes textile processing very difficult and consequently it is not commonly used in textiles, except for very low-grade products. The colour of cotton fibre varies from almost pure white to a dirty grey. However, the standard cotton grades classify colour as white, light spotted, spotted, tinged, yellow stained, and light grey. Highquality cotton is usually very light or almost white.

CULTIVATION AND GINNING

Cotton for commercial purposes is grown as an annual crop. Cotton is a warm-weather plant cultivated in both hemispheres, mostly in North and South America, Asia, Africa, and India (in tropical latitudes). The period from planting to harvesting is usually 5–7months. Planting time for cotton varies with locality, i.e. from February to June in the Northern Hemisphere. The time of planting in the Northern Hemisphere is harvest time in the Southern Hemisphere. After harvesting, the seed cotton (consisting of cotton fibre attached to cottonseed and foreign plant matter) is transported to the ginning plant. Ginning is the separation of the fibres from the seed and foreign plant matter such as dirt, twigs, leaves, and parts of bolls. Cotton essentially has no commercial value or use until the fibre is separated from the cottonseed and foreign matter at the gin. Ginning operations, which are regarded as part of the harvest rather than the textile process, normally include:

-conditioning (to adjust moisture content) -seed–fibre separation

-cleaning (to remove foreign plant matter) and-packaging.

There are two kinds of ginning: saw ginning and roller ginning. In saw gin, the saw-teeth removes seed and short fibre efficiently with a high production rate, butgreater damage to the fibres. In roller ginning, rollers gently separate the fibres from the seeds with less damage to the fibres, but the short fibres and foreign matter are not removed as efficiently reducing productivity. Usually, only the long–staple and high-quality cotton are ginned by roller gin where it is important

to prevent fibre damage. Most cottons, like Upland cotton, are ginned on saw gin. The long lint fibres are removed at the cotton gin and then packed into large bales and transferred

to spinning mills for further processing (spinning). The seed with about 8% short linter remaining is used for seed oil after the short linter fibres are removed by the delinting process, producing fibres of different lengths.

STRUCTURE OF COTTON

Each cotton fibre is a single complete cell that develops in the surface layer of the cottonseed. Cotton fibres are composed of a cuticle, a primary wall, a secondary wall, and a central core or lumen (Figure 2(b)). The cuticle is the 'very outside' or 'skin' of the cotton fibre. It is composed of a waxy layer (cotton wax). The lumen is a hollow canal running the length of the fibre, which provides the nutrients while the plant is growing. Depending on the maturity of the fibre, the dimensions of the lumen vary enormously. Mature fibres will have a thick layer of cellulose in the secondary wall that results in a very small lumen, whereas an immature fibre has a very thin wall structure and a large lumen. The longitudinal view of cotton fibre appears as a ribbon-like structure with twists at regular intervals along its length (Figure 2(b)). The twists, also called convolutions, give cotton an uneven fibre surface that increases interfibre friction and enables fine cotton yarns of adequate strength to be spun. The convolutions differentiate cotton fibres from all other forms of seed hair fibres and are partially responsible for many of cotton's unique characteristics. Cotton is soft, absorbent, strong, and machine-washable. Its absorbency comes from the fibre surface (which has a strong affinity for water), the fibre core microstructure (which resembles millions of tiny sponge-like tubes), and the hydroxyl (–OH) groups in its molecules. The width of cotton fibre is fairly uniform, varying between 12 and 20µm wide. The cross-section of cotton fibre is generally referred to as being kidney-shaped (Figure 2(a), Figure 3(a)), and some are elliptical. Mercerization (a process using caustic soda and tension) can cause the fibre to swell, straighten, and become more cylindrical, promoting lustre, dyeability, and increased strength. Mercerized

cotton is almost round in cross-section and more lustrous than untreated fibres. The degree of crystallite orientation, the microstructural parameter obtained by X-ray diffraction, is directly related to the bundle strength. In general, fibres with more highly oriented crystallinity are stronger and more rigid. Usually, the crystallinity of cotton ranges from 60% to 70%.

FIGURE

2

Microstructure of cotton. (a) Cross-section of cotton, (b) vertical section of cotton

FIGURE

3

Microscopic view of cotton fibre. (a) Cross-sectional view of cotton, (b) longitudinal view of cotton

COMPOSITION OF COTTON

Raw cotton fibre, after ginning and mechanical cleaning, contains approximately 90% or more cellulose (Table 1) and noncellulosics. Both the structure and composition of the cellulose and noncellulosics depend on the cotton variety and growing conditions.

The noncellulosic constituents of the fibre are located principally in the cuticle, the primary cell wall, and in the lumen. Cotton fibres that have a high ratio of surface area to linear density generally exhibit a higher noncellulosic content. The noncellulosic constituents include proteins, amino acids, other nitrogen-containing compounds, wax, pectic substances, organic acids, sugars, inorganic salts, and a very small amount of pigments. Variations in these constituents arise due to differences in fibre maturity, variety of cotton, and environmental conditions (soil, climate, farming practices, etc.). After treatments to remove the naturally occurring noncellulosic materials, the cellulose content of the fibre is over 99%.

Table 1 Composition of typical cotton fibres

Constituen	Typical (%)	Range (%)
Cellulose	95	88.0-96,0
Protein (% N× 6,25 *	1,3	1,1-1,9
Pectic substances	0,9	0,7-1,2
Ash	1,2	0,7-1,6
Wax	0,6	0,4-1,0
Total sugars	0,3	0,1-1,0
Organic acids	0,8	0,5-1,0
Pigment	Trace	-
Others	1,4	-

*Standard method of estimating percent protein from nitrogen content (%N)

PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF COTTON

High-quality cotton lint can produce high-quality yarn, fabric, and therefore high-quality end-products. High-quality cotton lint has a number of physical properties, some of which are measurable, whereas others are not. High-quality lint also implies the absence of certain harmful substances. The properties of cotton lint that are important and measurable include the following: -staple length -uniformity of fibre length-short fibre content (the percentage of short fibre) -fibre strength-fineness-maturity-elasticity (or elongation) and-for some cottons, colour. The properties of cotton lint that are not measurable include the following items:

- style
- silkeness and- lustre.

These are the main properties considered when cotton is classified or graded, and also affect the subsequent processing and quality of end-products. High-quality cotton is also characterized by low trash content. Cotton with a high trash content needs more drastic action during processing to clean the fibres, which may damage it, decreasing the quality of end-products.

Length and fineness of cotton fibre

The average length of cotton fibre used for textiles ranges from 25 to 37mm. The longer the fibre, the easier it is to process and the better the product's quality. Therefore, long-staple cotton has higher value in textile processing and is used for high-quality yarn or end-products. Being a natural product, the length of each cotton fibre may be different, and uniformity of fibre length is very important as the higher the uniformity, the better the fibre length. Short fibre content is the ratio of short fibre weight to the total tested fibre weight, which is also a key factor affecting processing. Short fibre usually refers to fibre shorter than a certain length. In HVI (high volume instrument) testing fibre less than 12.7 mm is considered to be short fibre and the higher the short fibre content the worse the fibre processing ability and lower the quality of

end-products. The fineness of fibres or yarns is usually expressed as the linear density of them (fibres or yarns), with the units of tex, dtex, or metric count. The tex corresponds to the fibre or yarn weight in grams of 10,000m length, whereas the metric count corresponds to the fibre or yarns in metres of the weight of a gram; the dtex (decitex) is 10th tex. The fineness of cotton fibre is usually in the range of 5000–7000 metric count, which is the finest of all the natural vegetable fibres.

Estimating fibre fineness and maturity (micronaire)

Direct measurement of biological fineness in terms of fibre or lumen diameter and cell-wall thickness are precluded by the high costs in both time and labour, the noncircular cross-sections of dry cotton fibres, and the high degree of variation in fibre fineness. Although advances in image analysis have improved measurements of biological fineness and maturity, fibre image analyses remain too slow and limited for fibres with irregular cross-sections so that this method is only really suitable for wool fibre with its almost regular circular cross-section. Instead, indirect indicators such as linear density are widely used to express the fineness of fibre. There are two commonly used methods to estimate the indirect fineness of cotton fibre. One is cut-middles method, and the other is airflow method. The cut-middles method The cut-middles method involves weighing and counting a number of fibres of a certain length so that the weight per length can be obtained giving the linear density of the fibre. Firstly, the fibre bundle, which has been weighed, is clamped at one end and then combed several times to remove the short fibres in the middle of the bundle. The fibre bundle is then cut between the neat and middle section into a certain fragment (for example, 10 or 20mm) which is weighed and the number of fibres in this section counted. The fibre fineness, referring to the definition, is then calculated. This method is also used for measuring many other types of fibre, only the length cut is different depending on the tested fibre. The air flow method The airflow method is based on the resistance of a bundle of fibres to airflow. Air-permeability of the sample depends on its surface area. Basic fluid-flow theory states that air permeability is inversely dependent on the square of the fibre surface area; therefore, empirical formulae were

developed for calculating the approximate weight per length (linear density) of the fibre. Due to its speed and ease of operation, this method is widely used to test the fineness of many kinds of fibres. The maturity of cotton fibre is closely related to its fineness, the immature fibre being finer. Therefore, micronaire, a comprehensive indicator of both the maturity and fineness of cotton fibre is the most commonly used instrumental fibre-quality test. Micronaire is mostly tested using the airflow method. HVI, AFIS, and some other instruments can be used to estimate the fineness and micronaire of the cotton. **The new era of fully automatized high volume instruments (HVI)**

A great deal of work has been and continues to be done developing devices and methods to ensure more comprehensive, objective cotton assessments. The first step in the transition to instrumental classing began with the introduction of the HVI line. Progress in the field of measuring systems is still important due to the growing competition of man-made fibres on the natural cottons. As a result of these developments, we have entered the new millennium with many fully automatized measurement systems like HVI Spectrum, AFIS, FiberLab, and Premier ART. Modern instruments allow measurement not only of the physical–mechanical parameters by the bundle or individual fibre methods, but also intrinsic properties like maturity, stickiness, color, and external factors influencing the cotton quality such as the cultivation, harvesting and ginning conditions like trash content, seed coat fragment content, and nep content. Now that all the measurement systems are fully automatized and computerized, we have a full database of fibre properties together with their images including other fibres, as well as cotton. These results are presented in [Table 2](#).

COTTON APPLICATION IN TEXTILE

The versatility of cotton has made it one of the most valuable and widely used of all textile fibres. Cotton is inherently strong because the convolutions create friction within the fabric, preventing the fibres from slipping. Wet cotton fabric is stronger than dry cotton fabric, therefore cotton can withstand repeated washings and is ideal for household goods and garments that need to be washed regularly. Like other celluloses

cotton cellulose is not unduly affected by moderate heat so that cotton fabrics can be ironed with a hot iron without damage. Cotton fibres are able to absorb appreciable amounts of moisture and then evaporate it readily to the air which adds to the comfort of cotton garments. There are literally thousands of uses (about 100 major uses) for cotton in textile items, ranging from nappies to the most fashionable dresses, coats, and jackets. These uses can be classified into three main categories: apparel, home furnishings, and industrial.

1. Apparel market: Due to cotton’s comfort and easy laundering, trousers and shirts, especially for leisure wear, account for the greatest use of cotton, followed by underwear. Jeans and denim fabrics utilize more cotton than any other single clothing item.

2. Home furnishings: The absorbency of cotton makes it an excellent material for household fabrics such as sheets and towels. Towels and flannels account for the largest amount of cotton used in home furnishings, followed by sheets and pillowcases.

3. Industrial products: The uses of cotton in industrial products are as diverse as tarpaulins, bookbindings, and zipper tapes. Cotton products are also used to clean up agrochemical spills and oil spills. Some of the major industrial markets for cotton are medical supplies and industrial threads.

Table 2 The fully automatized and computerized measurement systems

Basic fibre properties measured	STI 2020 data products	Shaffner tech. Inc. ISO tester 2003	Uster technologies Inc. HVI spectrum 2003	Uster technologies AFIS	Uster technologies, Intelli Gin	Lintronics fibrelab 2003	Premier polytronics premier ART (Automatic Rapid Tester) 2003	Premier HFT 9000
Micronaire	Mic	Mic	Mic	-		Mic	Mic	Mic

Length	UHM LU SFC	UHM, inch, mm LU	UHM LU SFI	L(w), L(n) UQL(w), SFC(n) SFC(w), L(n)CV LCV(w)	-	L(w) UI SFI	CL(w) SFC Premier aQur	SL, L(w)
Strength	Strength, g/tex Elongation, %	Strength, g/tex	Strength, g/tex Elongation, %	-	-	Strength Elongation	Strength Elongation	Strength Elongation
Colour	CIE (fibre only) Colour grade	Rd, +b Colour grade	Colour +b, Rd Colour grade	-	Colour	Colour +b, Rd Colour grade	Rd, +b	Rd, +b
Trash	% Area Leaf grade Size dist. Bark and grass extraneous	% Area Leaf grade	% Area Leaf grade Trash	Trash Cnt/g Dust Cnt/g VFM Mean size	Trash	Trash Cnt/g Trash size Trash area Dust Cnt/g	Trash	-

	us matt er prep arati on							
Moistur e content	%	%	%	-	%	-	-	-
Neps, seed coat fragmen ts	Nep s/g Size dist. Seed coat frag men ts	Neps/g	Neps	Nep Cnt/g Nep size SCN Cnt/g SCN size	-	Nep Cnt/g Nep area Npe size SCN/ g SCN area SCN size	Neps (Premier aQura)	-
Maturit y and fineness	Mat ratio Imm atur e fibre fract ion		Matu rity index	Maturi ty ratio Finene ss IFC		Matu rity index	Maturity estimate	
Stickine ss	Stic ky poin ts/g Size Sug ar type s	Sticky points/g	-	-	-	Stick y mass Cnt Stick iness grad Stick iness size	-	-

SUMMARY

Natural fibres include vegetable fibres and protein fibres. Among the natural fibres, cotton, which is finer and softer than the other vegetable fibres, has the largest production and widest application. The main component of vegetable fibre is cellulose, so that all the natural vegetable fibres have similar characteristics of high water absorbency, low resilience, a tendency to wrinkle easily, resistance to alkalies and organic solvents, and are highly combustible. All bast fibres have non-cellulose matters or gums besides the main components of cellulose; therefore, before being further processed, degumming or retting is needed to remove (at least part of) the gums. The high content of lignin in bast fibres means they are usually harder and less elastic than cotton.

In this chapter, the most commonly used natural cellulose fibers are introduced. The structure, composition, property, and main application of these fibers are described, the basic and main test methods for the fibers are also mentioned. It is hoped to make the learner better understand the characteristic and application of the natural fibers, the most commonly used natural cellulose fibers are introduced. The structure, composition, property, and main application of these fibers are described, the basic and main test methods for the fibers are also mentioned. It is hoped to make the learner better understand the characteristic and application of the natural fibers.

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